

The role of zinc in human physiology

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Abstract

Zinc (Zn) is important from body due to its role in physiological processes through its catalytic, structural, and regulatory functions defined as a trace element. Although its level is lower, Zn is maintained by a modulating system involving Zn transporters (ZnTs and ZIPs), intracellular buffering and muffling mechanisms, organellar sequestration, and Zn-binding proteins such as metallothioneins (MTs) and thionein (T). Beyond its classical role as a cofactor for metalloenzymes, Zn act intracellular signal transmitter in cell therefore influencing cell proliferation, apoptosis, neurotransmission, immune responses, and redox homeostasis. Zn-dependent zinc finger (ZF) motifs further link Zn availability to transcriptional regulation and hormone signaling pathways. Additionally, Zn modulates key signaling cascades, including Nrf 2 and NF-κB-mediated pathways, thereby contributing to antioxidant defense and inflammatory control. Disruption of Zn homeostasis has been associated with a wide range of metabolic, neurological, immunological, and endocrine disorders. This review asserts a comprehensive aspect of Zn metabolism, intracellular storage, and physiological functions, highlighting the central role of Zn in maintaining cellular and systemic homeostasis.

Keywords: Zinc, metallothioneins, thionein

Introduction

Trace element is identified that minerals and are required in only 0.01% of body weight, and also responses various biological process required normal physiological conditions in the body, which are taken in the diet. They taken body with nutrient via the gastrointestinal system, and poor consumption leads to its insufficiency. Total parental nutrition, genetic predispositions, malabsorption syndromes, or poor nutrition result in current structural or biochemical deficiencies¹. Zinc (Zn) is a metal has belong to the trace element category, with a normal 12–18 μmol/L in plasma, commonly diminished in diseases and/or total parental nutrition. Zn taken the roles to a world of biological process including hundreds of enzyme functions, regulation of DNA metabolism, immunological response, cell proliferation and differentiation, signal transmission, and genetic expression.^{1,2} Due to this, deficiency of Zn results in reduced of muscle capacity, immune dysfunction, anorexia, diarrhea, loss of hair, dermatitis, depression, latency in wound healing, etc.¹ These multiple effects of Zn in metabolism show that it is an indispensable ion and investigating effects of Zn is crucial. In this review its aimed at reporting metabolism and physiological functions of Zn.

Metabolism of Zn

The average 1.4–2.3 g Zn is in the adult body, that descending sort of skeletal muscles, bones, liver, skin, and other tissues.^{3,4} The Zn amount per gram of tissue is

represented in Table 1.

Table 1. Zn amount per gram of tissue.⁵

Tissue	Zn amount (μg/g)
Pankreas	140
Bone	100
Liver	58
Kidney	55
Muscle	51
Skin	32
Heart	23
Brain	11

The majority of ingested Zn is absorbed at the duodenum and jejunum. Absorbed Zn crosses the liver directly via the portal system; on the other hand, a minor part of Zn linkage in metallothionein (MT) inside the enterocytes. Its absorption depends on various factor that affects transporters localized with enterocytes in the apical membrane. The citric acid facilitates whereas iron, fiber, and a Zn chelator of phytate inhibit the Zn absorption. Due to that, bioavailability depends not only on the usage of the body but also on absorption. If the concentration of Zn is more than the requirement, it removes the body various ways. Approximately 4 μg/mL of Zn excreted with bile, and 4 μg/mL of Zn is removed via uriner system. Skin, hair, and the gastrointestinal system are other ways to eliminate from the body for a small

amount of Zn.^{3,4,6}

Transport of Zn

The Zn ion cannot cross the cellular membranes because it is a charged kation divalent cation. Therefore, transfer of Zn occurs via transporters that consist of two main families known as Zn Transporters (ZnT) and Zrt-Irt-like Protein (ZIP). ZnT encodes the SLC30A1-10 gene in the human and comprises 10 homolog transporter that provide excretion of Zn from the cytoplasm. The other family is identified as ZIP, synthesized from SLC39A1-14 genes, and includes 14 homolog transporters that take Zn inside the cell. Therefore, both protein families support cellular Zn homeostasis, as localisation and flow ways given in Figure 1.^{7,8}

Zn is stable in the +2 ionic form inside the cell rather than other metal ions due to the d circle being fully in the form.⁹ Although the form is stable, the intracellular level of Zn that is 24 pmol/L in erythrocytes, is crucial for cell viability. The higher levels of Zn that dose of IC₅₀ is 80 pmol/L leads to inhibition of Ca-ATPase. Due to this reason, minimal changes in Zn ions are regulated by two main mechanisms.¹⁰⁻¹² Buffering is the first mechanism of diminishing Zn level that exists via the linkage of Zn to intracellular protein.^{10,11} The second mechanism is known as muffling, that happened instable Zn ion level. The unrestricted extrusion of ions from the cell involves a series of events, including their transport into organelles and/or cytosolic buffering. In contrast with thermodynamic buffering procedures, time-dependent flow muffling includes slower ion sequestration and extrusion.¹¹ Both mechanisms prevent cellular Zn toxicity through controlling the ion concentration.¹²

Intracellular Zn Storage

The Zn ions storage various organel including mitochondria, nucleus, Golgi, endosomes/vesicles and lysosomes due to the Zn concentration regulation.¹¹ According to a study on cortical neurons, it is revealed that reducing cytosolic Zn leads to storage on the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and Golgi.¹³ Lysosomes represent another intracellular organelle in which Zn is stored, and this sequestration reduces lysosomal membrane permeabilization, thereby contributing to cellular prote-

ction against Zn toxicity-induced cell death.¹³⁻¹⁵ Another subcellular compartment in which Zn is localized is the mitochondrion. Zn is transported into mitochondria via the mitochondrial calcium uniporter. In addition, activation of TRPC6 channels promotes the release of Zn from mitochondrial stores in concert with calcium.^{15,16} Zn is compartmentalized within stored intracellular vesicles or regulated release and within vesicles of secretion for exocytosis. These Zn-enriched vesicles, known as zincosomes, assist in regulating intracellular Zn homeostasis by limiting fluctuations in cytosolic Zn ion concentrations.^{17,18}

Intracellular Zn ions regulates with proteins that have a high affinity for Zn are present within the cell, and these proteins not only function as Zn-sensitive elements or participate in Zn transport but also contribute directly to the maintenance of Zn homeostasis.^{5,19} Among these proteins, metallothioneins (MTs) represent a key component.²⁰ MTs have a high cysteine content, low-molecular-weight also absence of aromatic amino acids, so a structural composition that confers a high capacity for binding metal ions, particularly Zn, through thiol groups.²¹ Each MT molecule has the ability to connect to seven Zn ions.²⁰ MT expression is regulated by intracellular Zn levels, and in humans, 11 functional MT isoforms have been identified, which divide into the following categories: MT-1 through MT-4²² MT-1 consists of eight distinct paralogs and is expressed in nearly all tissues. MT-2, which has a single isoform, exhibits a similar expression pattern to MT-1. MT-3 and MT-4, on the other hand, are both encoded by a single gene and exhibit tissue-specific expression; MT-4 occurs primarily in epithelial cells, whereas MT-3 is primarily expressed in the brain.²³

Thionein (T), the apoform of MT, is a potent Zn-binding molecule. Zn can be transferred bidirectionally between MT and T.²⁴ Owing to this property, the MT/T system functions as a regulatory control mechanism for intracellular Zn concentrations (Figure 2).²¹ The high reactivity of T toward sulfur ligands, its limited stability when bound to Zn, and its ability to permit Zn release from MT are critical factors in maintaining this balance. It has been estimated that about 20% of cytosolic Zn interacts with apoprotein Ts to generate MTs.^{21,24}

Figure 1. Zn transporters and their cellular localisations.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the dynamic balance between metallothionein (MT) and thionein (T).

Zinc in Enzymatic Function

The biochemical importance of Zn was first recognized in the 1930s with the discovery of its crucial function in the carbonic anhydrase enzyme activity in erythrocytes. Approximately fifteen years later, Zn was also identified as a constituent of the bovine carboxypeptidase enzyme. On account of advances in analytical and isolation techniques, it has become widely accepted that Zn is vital to the function of numerous enzymes.^{12,25} The enzymes influenced by Zn can be classified into six main groups: isomerases, hydrolases, lyases, transferases, ligases, and oxidoreductases. The distribution of these enzymes is presented in Figure 3, and as clearly illustrated in the figure, they predominantly exhibit high levels of catalytic activity. In a study investigating Zn-containing enzymes, their functional activities were systematically analyzed. The results demonstrated that 64% of these enzymes possess catalytic functions, 22% have structural roles, 10% exhibit both catalytic and structural properties, and 1% function as substrates or regulatory elements. For the remaining 3%, their functions could not be fully categorized.²⁶

Aferomentioned properities of Zn-dependent enzymes have been identified for their roles in essential cellular processes, including cell division, DNA synthesis, and a wide range of catalytic reactions.²⁵ Acting as a Lewis acid

reagent in redox and biological reactions under physiological conditions enables Zn to fulfill these functional roles.⁴

Zn as an Intracellular Messenger

Zn ions play a role in modulating cellular processes, including apoptosis. Similarly, calcium, this function is mediated through its direct interactions with enzymes.¹⁷ By activating intracellular signaling molecules, Zn imitate to hormones, growth factors, and cytokines. In fact, Zn could be identified nanomolar-range inhibitor of protein tyrosine phosphatases (PTPs). Moreover, Zn is a regulator for transcription factors, and it induces the expression of numerous genes. Among these are genes involved in Zn homeostasis, including those encoding Zn transporters and metallothioneins (MTs).²⁷ It has been reported that one of the factors whose transcription is influenced by Zn is the nuclear-localized zinc transporter ZIP6.²⁸ Moreover, Zn has been shown to exert effects on numerous enzymes, receptors, and regulatory factors, as summarized in Table 2.²⁹

Table 2. Molecular targets affected by Zn.

Target Structure	Effect	Reference
Protein tyrosine phosphatases	Inhibition	30
Insulin/IGF-1 receptor Insulin receptor substrate-1	Tyrosine phosphorylation	30
Epidermal growth factor receptor	Activation	31
Transcription factor FOXO1a	Activation	32
Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK)	Activation	33

A study in mouse embryonic stem cells demonstrated that Zn regulates cell proliferation by modulating multiple intracellular signaling pathways, including mTOR, p44/42 MAPKs, PI3K/Akt, and JNK/SAPK.³⁴ Accordingly, it reveals that Zn may act in a manner analogous to a

Figure 3. Distribution of zinc enzymes among the enzyme classes and their functions.

primary messenger.³⁵ Taken together, Zn is regarded as an messenger molecule inside the cell.^{27,35}

Zinc as a Neurotransmitter

Excitatory neuronal activity triggers the extracellular release of Zn that influences neighboring postsynaptic neurons and glial cells by modulating intercellular signaling, thereby contributing to neurotransmission.^{27,36,37} Furthermore, Zn is accepted as a ligand for the orphan receptor GPR39 and is reported to mediate metabotropic signaling in hippocampal neurons via the Zn/GPR39 pathway.³⁸ In addition to its direct effects, Zn also indirectly modulates cellular signaling activity. This modulation is primarily mediated through key membrane transporters and ion channels, including dopamine transporters, AMPA (α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid), NMDA (N-methyl-D-aspartate), GABA-A (γ -aminobutyric acid type A), glycine, and purinergic receptors. Moreover, store-operated calcium (SOC) channels contain high-affinity Zn binding sites.^{39,40}

Physiological Functions

The three primary categories of Zn's physiological functions are structural, regulatory, and catalytic. Zn functions as a positive regulator through approximately three hundred metalloenzymes. These enzymes are essential for reactive oxygen species (ROS), carbohydrate, lipid, and protein metabolism. Moreover, Zn is a constituent of integral proteins, nucleic acids, and some organelles that are found in ribosomes and cellular membranes. Moreover, Zn exerts regulatory functions in the control of gene transcription, cell signaling, hormone secretion, and apoptotic processes.⁶

Zn has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory roles that are key regulators of redox homeostasis. The activity leads to antioxidant enzymes that include Zn. In addition, Zn has been shown to suppress pro-oxidant activity at sufficient intracellular concentrations and modulate the Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf 2) pathway. From an anti-inflammatory perspective, Zn modulates inflammatory signaling primarily by regulating the NF- κ B pathway and its downstream proinflammatory cytokines. Also, Zn has been reported to influence the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines. Clinically, the combined antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions of Zn have been associated with reduced circulating levels of C-reactive protein.^{41,42}

Another regulatory role of Zn ions is their involvement in the immune system. Zn has a vital role in immune system development, as well as in immune cell proliferation and migration. Furthermore, Zn has been shown to participate in B-cell-mediated immune functions, including antibody production, phagocytosis, and antigen presentation.⁴¹

Zinc Fingers and Their Role in Steroid Hormone Synthesis

One of the most prominent physiological functions of Zn ions is their involvement in the regulation of DNA transcription, a role that was established in the 1980s. Zinc finger (ZF) motifs were first identified in eukaryotic cells and are nucleoprotein domains typically composed

of approximately 30 amino acids enriched in cysteine and histidine residues. These structures function as regulatory elements in transcription, DNA replication, and DNA repair processes. Based on the combination and arrangement of their coordinating residues, several subtypes exist in ZF. Among these, the C2H2-type ZFs, which are referred to as classical ZFs, include two cysteine and two histidine residues. Classical ZFs primarily serve as DNA-binding domains, and transcriptional regulation occurs from the area.^{21,43-45} Similar ZF motifs have been identified in nuclear hormone receptors for steroid hormones. Therefore, androgen, estrogen, and progesterone metabolism are changed in Zn deficiency, which may be attributed to the impaired function of ZF proteins acting at the level of membrane-associated or nuclear receptors.²¹

Conclusion

Zn is a multifunctional trace element that has indispensable roles in human physiology through its catalytic, structural, and regulatory functions. As outlined in this review, Zn homeostasis is strictly controlled by coordinated mechanisms involving ZnTs and ZIPs, intracellular buffering and muffling processes, organellar sequestration, and Zn-binding proteins such as MTs and T. Beyond its classical role as a structural component of metalloenzymes, Zn has emerged as a dynamic intracellular signaling molecule and neuromodulator, influencing key cellular processes including proliferation, apoptosis, neurotransmission, immune regulation, and redox balance.

In conclusion, aforementioned information bring to light about Zn physiology. Based on these, to prevent and treatment the disease, Zn should be considered.

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